

The use of statistical features for low-rate denial of service attack detection

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Abstract

Low-rate Denial of Service (LDoS) attacks can significantly reduce network performance. These attacks involve sending periodic high-intensity pulse data flows, sharing similar harmful effects with traditional DoS attacks. However, LDoS attacks have different attack modes, making detection particularly challenging. The high level of concealment associated with LDoS attacks makes them extremely difficult to identify using traditional DoS detection methods. In this paper, we explore the potential of using statistical features for LDoS attack detection. Our results demonstrate the promising performance of statistical features in detecting these attacks. Furthermore, through ANOVA, Mutual Information, RFE, and SHAP analysis, we find that entropy and L-moment-based features play a crucial role in LDoS attack detection. These findings provide valuable insights into utilizing statistical features enhancing network security, thereby improving overall resilience and stability of networks against various types of attacks.

Keywords: Low-rate DDoS attack, Feature engineering, Machine learning, Explainable AI

1 Introduction

Service availability is a pivotal asset for service providers that needs protection against cyber threats [1]. Availability refers to a server's ability to provide uninterrupted services to legitimate users on demand. With the evolution towards 5G, 6G, and future mobile network iterations, ensuring uninterrupted services becomes even more critical due to the increased complexities and expanded attack surfaces introduced by these advanced technologies. The higher speeds, lower latency, and massive connectivity anticipated in these networks necessitate robust security measures to defend against sophisticated threats and maintain continuous service delivery to legitimate users. Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks pose a significant threat to service availability. Attackers use a large number of compromised devices or bots on the network to overwhelm the server, depleting its resources and denying service to legitimate clients.

DDoS attacks are generally categorized into high-rate DDoS and Low-rate DoS (LDoS) attacks [2]. High-rate DDoS attacks cause a rapid growth in traffic volume, making it easy to differentiate from legitimate traffic. In contrast, LDoS attacks use low-rate traffic, similar to legitimate traffic, making it difficult to discriminate and detect such traffic patterns [2]. LDoS attacks do not require extensive resources to execute and can be launched from a single malicious device. They often target HTTP but can attack any TCP-based service with long-lived TCP sessions that have slow transfer rates [3].

HTTP protocol plays a crucial role in networks specially, in emerging mobile technologies such as 5G and beyond. 5G mobile technology deploys HTTP protocol to carry out the communication between the Network Functions (NFs) and Application Functions (AFs) in the core network (5GC) which is based on Service-Based Architecture (SBA). The core network establishes reliable, secure connectivity for end users and provides access to its services. The core domain handles various essential functions in the mobile network, including connectivity and mobility management, authentication and authorization, subscriber data management and policy management, among others [4]. Although several security and privacy arrangements have been defined in the 3GPP standard for 5G core network, the vulnerability of the HTTP protocol to LDoS attacks leaves the core network susceptible to such types of attacks.

Although several techniques have been proposed in literature to detect DDoS attacks [5], LDoS attacks exhibits a high degree of stealth. Therefore, the majority of studies lack sensitivity for LDoS attack detection, resulting low detection performance with respect to false positive and true positive rates. While frequency domain analysis methods such as discrete Fourier transform [6] and wavelet transform [7] show promising performance for LDoS attack detection, they impose computational overhead to the underlying system. Consequently, some memory and CPU resources are required to spare to run such detection methods. The use of statistical features, such as statistical momentum, has shown promising results for high-rate DDoS attack detection [8]. Therefore, in this study, we aim to investigate the use of statistical features for LDoS attack detection. Our main goal is to investigate the potential use of statistical features for detecting LDoS attacks. We investigate the use of statistical features obtained from time-series data generated from network statistics, combined with Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, for LDoS attack detection. Several statistics

including mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis, entropy, the Hurst parameter, and L-moments, are employed in this study. Skewness and kurtosis, known as the third and the fourth moments in statistics, are used to analyze the symmetry and flatness of a probability distribution, respectively [9]. Entropy serves as a measure of the amount of uncertainty and randomness in a probability distribution [10]. Self-similarity, a property associated with fractals, characterizes objects whose properties remain consistent regardless of the viewing scale [11]. To quantify self-similarity, the Hurst exponent, \mathcal{H} , is utilized. It measures the amount of long-term memory present in a time-series.

L-moments are the collection of statistical measures that provide a method for describing the shape, location, and size of a probability distribution. Developed as alternatives to traditional moments in statistical analysis, L-moments utilize a combination of order statistics of a distribution and are designed to exhibit greater resilience to outliers than moments. Among L-moments, the first, λ_1 , and second, λ_2 , have conventional names as L-mean and L-scale, respectively. Another crucial parameter for L-moment is the L-moment ratio or scaled L-moment. Particularly significant among these ratios are τ_3 and τ_4 , known as L-skewness and L-kurtosis, respectively. Compared to moments of a distribution, L-moments are more robust to outliers [12].

To investigate the contribution of each individual feature to the prediction, we employ four feature selection methods: The Analysis Of Variance [13], Mutual Information [14], Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) [15] method, and the Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) [16] explainable AI method. These methods help to identify the most impactful features, enabling informed decisions regarding feature selection and enhancing the interpretability of our LDoS attack detection system. When evaluating the potential usage of statistical moments for LDoS attack detection, the choice of an appropriate dataset is crucial. The CIC-IDS2017 dataset stands out as the best option due to its large, comprehensive, and realistic traffic data, labeled information, reproducibility, and widespread adoption. Therefore, we utilize the CIC-IDS2017 dataset [17] for our investigation.

Our main contributions are listed as follows:

- First, we extract the time-series representation of various network statistics from the network traffic
- Second, we obtain a set of statistical features, including mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis, entropy, the Hurst parameter, and L-moments. Our aim is to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing insights into the applicability and effectiveness of statistical moments as a fundamental feature set for LDoS attack detection.
- Third, we apply feature engineering methods to identify the optimal feature set for LDoS attack detection
- Fourth, we use the selected features as the input for ML algorithms to differentiate attack from legitimate traffic.
- Finally, we investigate the contribution of features to the final prediction using ANOVA, Mutual Information, RFE and SHAP.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we review related work on LDoS attack detection techniques. We explain the methodology in Section 3.

We discuss the results in Section 4. We analyse the computational complexity cost of calculating statistical features in Section 5. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section 6.

2 Related work

Since the emergence of LDoS in 2001, this attack has gained considerable attention and many researchers have made significant efforts to develop defenses against it [18]. In general, detection approaches for LDoS mainly rely on flow-based analysis of network traffic. Several statistics are sampled from the flow and then utilized in either the time or frequency domain to detect LDoS traffic. Wu et al. [19] extract the combined features of LDoS attack traffic and input them into a neural network classifier to detect LDoS attacks. They verify the effectiveness of their method through both simulation platforms and experimental networks. Zhang et al. [20] combine Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Support Vector Machine (SVM) models for LDoS attack detection. They use PCA to filter out noise interference and extract the primary features of TCP flows, which are then used to train SVM models. Yan et al. [21] extract features such as mean, variance, and entropy to train improved logistic regression models for detecting LDoS attacks. TANG et al. [22] apply deep learning technology to calculate the reconstruction error of traffic sequences for detecting LDoS attacks. Tang et al. [23] introduce a new approach for detecting LDoS attacks using data mining technology to analyze abnormal network traffic. Their method includes the establishment of judgment benchmarks and experimental simulations on both simulated and physical environments, as well as public datasets to validate its effectiveness. The results demonstrate that the detection method is capable of effectively identifying LDoS attacks while maintaining an optimal detection cost and low complexity. Shi et al. [24] proposes an LDoS attack detection method for cloud based on SVM. The method is verified using simulation and test-bed environments.

In Frequency domain-based detection approaches, statistics obtained from network traffic are transformed into the frequency domain using methods such as discrete Fourier analysis [25] or wavelet transform [26]. These transformed statistics are then utilized to detect LDoS samples. Zhang et al. [27] propose a detection algorithm for LDoS attacks based on the Power Spectral Density (PSD) entropy function and SVM. The algorithm estimates the PSD-entropy to detect the attack and compares it with two adaptive thresholds. To reduce costs and improve detection efficiency, the SVM is employed to learn the pattern. Agrawal et al. [28] utilize a power spectral density-based method to identify low-speed LDoS attacks in cloud environments. They use time-domain data, apply Fourier transform to the frequency domain, and calculate the power spectral density values. If the power spectral density is concentrated in the low-frequency band, the traffic is classified as an attack. Brynielsson [29] attempts to detect LDoS attacks on application servers using spectral analysis based on the continuous connection feature in the HTTP protocol. While spectrum classification is an effective approach for LDoS attack detection, the signal conversion process can lead to high computational overhead, as well as high false alarm and undetected rates.

Statistical features play a crucial role in the classification of network traffic [8]. These features provide essential information that can be used to identify specific types of traffic, such as LDoS attacks. In this study, we contribute to the existing research by analyzing several key statistical features for LDoS attack detection. Additionally, we investigate which features are the primary contributors to detection accuracy by employing four feature importance analysis methods, Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA), Mutual Information, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) and, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) analysis. Our analysis provides valuable insights into the importance of different statistical features for LDoS attack detection and can help improve the accuracy and efficiency of detection methods. This study represents an extension of our prior work presented at the 2nd International Conference on 6G Networking (6GNet) conference [30]. We enhance our previous study by incorporating ANOVA and mutual information methods alongside RFE and SHAP analysis to gain deeper insights into the contributions of individual statistical features to the final decision. Furthermore, we introduce a computational complexity cost analysis to compare the computational cost associated with estimating each statistical feature

3 Methodology

Figure 1 provides an overview of the proposed solution. In the initial stage, network-related features are collected to generate the first feature set. Subsequently, the preprocessing phase commences with the objective of acquiring more distinctive and informative features. Following this, statistical features are extracted to form a feature set that conveys information about the underlying probability distribution of network traffic, enabling the differentiation of LDoS attack traffic from normal traffic. Once features are extracted, they are used by an ML model to identify LDoS traffic samples. In the subsequent subsections, we delve into further details concerning the preprocessing and statistical feature extraction modules.

Fig. 1: Proposed solution.

3.1 Preprocessing phase

The goal of feature selection is to identify the most relevant and discriminative feature set from the original dataset, significantly improving the accuracy and efficiency of subsequent classification models. In this study, feature selection is performed using

correlation analysis and variance thresholding. Highly correlated features contain similar information, thereby providing limited additional advantage for the classification task. Furthermore, the highly correlated features may lead to instability in the final classification model and increase sensitivity to new data [31]. To address this issue, we employ a two-step process. Firstly, we utilize the correlation matrix to find highly correlated features and discard them. Secondly, we apply a variance threshold to eliminate features with low variance. The variance threshold method is a fundamental technique for feature selection, involving the removal of any features whose variance does not meet a certain threshold. By default, this threshold eliminates features with zero variance, indicating that they have the same value in all samples. The underlying assumption is that features with higher variance likely contain more valuable information.

3.2 Statistical Feature Extraction phase

To differentiate between benign traffic and LDoS attacks, we assume that statistics obtained from network traffic may follow different probability distributions during an LDoS attack compared to normal traffic. This assumption is reasonable because normal traffic data is typically generated by legitimate users and follows a certain pattern, whereas attack traffic data is generated by attackers and can exhibit different patterns or behaviors. Statistical features are valuable for in defining probability distributions as they provide information about the central tendency, variability, and shape of the data. Moreover, these features can serve as inputs to machine learning algorithms for classification or prediction tasks. In the next phase, after eliminating extra network statistics during the preprocessing phase, we extract various statistical features for each network statistics. To this end, first, all data samples arriving at the same timestamp are identified. For each specific time stamp, t , several features including the mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis, entropy, Hurst parameters, and L-moment-related features are estimated. Subsequently, a new feature set is extracted to discriminate LDoS traffic from benign traffic. Each feature can be represented as a time-series, generated by estimating its elements for each time interval t .

4 Discussion and Result

In this section, we discuss the results of the feature engineering process and the application of machine learning on the obtained features. To thoroughly investigate the potential usage of statistical moments for LDoS attack detection, it is crucial to select an appropriate dataset that can provide reliable and meaningful evaluation results. Among the available options, the CIC-IDS2017 [17] dataset stands out as the ideal choice for our study.

The CIC-IDS2017 dataset offers a wealth of advantages that make it highly suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of statistical moments in LDoS attack detection. Firstly, it provides a large and comprehensive collection of real traffic data, encompassing diverse network scenarios and capturing the intricacies of both normal and attack traffic patterns. This rich dataset ensures that our evaluation covers a wide range of

Table 1: The final list of the network traffic statistics.

No	Feature	No	Feature	No	Feature	No	Feature
1	Flow Duration	2	Total Fwd Packets	3	Total Length of Fwd Packets	4	Fwd Packet Length Max
5	Bwd Packet Length Max	6	Flow IAT Max	7	Flow IAT Min	8	Fwd IAT Min
9	Fwd Packets/s	10	Bwd Packets/s	11	Max Packet Length	12	Down/Up Ratio
13	Average Packet Size	14	Init.Win.bytes.forward	15	Init.Win.bytes.backward	16	min_seg.size.forward

real-world scenarios, allowing us to gauge the robustness and effectiveness of statistical moments in detecting LDoS attacks.

Furthermore, the CIC-IDS2017 dataset offers the valuable advantage of labeled data. Each network flow in the dataset is annotated with ground truth labels indicating whether it corresponds to normal traffic or a specific type of attack. This labeling enables accurate performance evaluation by allowing us to compare the predictions made by our statistical moment-based detection approach with the known ground truth. Such evaluation ensures a comprehensive assessment of the detection rates, false positives, false negatives, and other performance metrics, thereby providing meaningful insights into the effectiveness of statistical moments for LDoS attack detection. Therefore, CIC-IDS2017 serves as the baseline for this study. The dataset comprises both benign (normal) traffic and common low-rate DDoS attacks, including Slowloris, Slowhttptest, Hulk, and GoldenEye attacks. Due to the similarity of the data to real-world traffic data, we have chosen this dataset for our study. It contains 84 traffic statistics as features.

The approach in this study is based on flow analysis, which focuses on the overall behavior of the network traffic rather than the characteristics of individual packets. Therefore, features such as source IP address and port number are discarded, as they are considered to be packet-level characteristics and not relevant for flow analysis.

Once the irrelevant features are discarded, in the first phase, the correlation matrix of the dataset is estimated, and the threshold for highly correlated columns is set to $th_c = 90\%$; therefore, those columns with a higher correlation than th_c are eliminated. By applying this criterion, the number of columns in the dataset is decreased from 84 to 58. In the next step, the columns with low variance are discarded. To this end, the threshold for variance is empirically chosen as $th_v = 0.06$, and all columns with variance less than th_v are not considered for feature extraction. At the end of the feature selection phase, a dataset with 16 columns is obtained, which are listed in Table 1

In the next phase of the analysis, each column of the dataset is thoroughly scrutinized, and 11 statistical features are computed for every individual column. These statistical characteristics aid in extracting vital insights regarding the probability distribution of the data present in each column. The acquired information can then be leveraged to differentiate between legitimate traffic and LDoS traffic. Consequently, the outcome is a new dataset that comprises a total of 176 statistical features.

To gain a deeper comprehension of the importance of individual statistical features, they are grouped into distinct sets based on their feature type. Subsequently, each set is subjected to a binary hypothesis test, which enables the assessment of its

Table 2: The result of binary hypothesis test.

Feature	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Entropy	Hurst parameter	λ_2	λ_3	λ_4	τ_3	τ_4
Accuracy (%)	97.2	98.7	97.1	89.9	99.3	91.2	98.6	97.8	91.7	98	89.2

efficacy in differentiating LDoS samples from legitimate traffic samples. This evaluation helps to measure the discriminatory power of each feature set and provides a clearer understanding of their relevance in identifying malicious traffic.

Table 2 summarizes the outcomes of the binary hypothesis test, revealing that the entropy features demonstrate the highest efficacy in distinguishing between LDoS and legitimate traffic. Additionally, the standard deviation feature, as well as the λ_2 and τ_3 features, also exhibit a significant level of discrimination ability. To further validate the effectiveness of these four highly discriminatory statistical features, namely entropy, standard deviation, λ_2 , and τ_3 , principal component analysis (PCA) is utilized on each feature set. PCA is a statistical technique that facilitates dimensionality reduction of a dataset while retaining the maximum amount of variation in the data. In this scenario, each feature set is condensed to three dimensions, and the resulting outcomes are displayed in Figure 2. The figure shows a clear segregation between LDoS traffic and legitimate traffic within the compressed dimensional space, underscoring the high effectiveness of the aforementioned four features in identifying and distinguishing between the two types of traffic.

While the binary hypothesis test provides valuable information on the performance of each statistical feature set in distinguishing LDoS traffic from legitimate traffic, it has limitations. The test assumes that the data is normally distributed and that the variances are equal between the two groups. However, these assumptions may not always hold true in practice. Moreover, binary hypothesis tests are not suitable for building robust and accurate models for real-world scenarios. Therefore, it is important to use machine learning algorithms to further analyze the dataset and build models that can accurately classify LDoS traffic. We assess the effectiveness of the feature set using various ML algorithms, including K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), SVM, Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost, Naive Bayes (NB), and Linear Discriminating Analysis (LDA). The performance results of the detection are summarized in Table 3. Based on the table, it can be inferred that the outcomes of all ML algorithms are acceptable, indicating that the feature set obtained is not dependent on any particular ML model and can be utilized by any ML model to classify LDoS attacks.

It is essential to understand which features the models use to make their predictions. Therefore, in the next phase, we utilize four techniques to identify the most relevant features that contribute to the accuracy of the classification task: ANOVA, Mutual information, RFE, and SHAP. ANOVA has a crucial role in pinpointing features that display significant differences among different categories. By assessing the F-statistic for each feature, ANOVA effectively emphasizes the features that make a substantial contribution to distinguishing between DDoS attacks and legitimate traffic. This method primarily aims to capture variations in feature values that carry essential discriminative information. Figure 3 presents a visualization of the top ten features that play a significant role in LDoS attack detection. The figure highlights

(a) Entropy.

(b) Standard Deviation.

(c) λ_2 .

(d) τ_3 .

Fig. 2: PCA results for the four most discriminatory statistical features.

Table 3: The performance result of applying ML algorithms on statistical feature set.

Classifier	FPr (%)	TPr (%)	ACC (%)	F1_score
KNN	11.76	99.2	97.9	0.91
SVM	5.88	99.21	98.6	0.94
DT	0	100	100	1
RF	5.88	100	99.3	0.97
AdaBoost	0	100	100	1
NB	11.76	99.21	97.9	0.91
LDA	5.88	100	99.3	0.97

that the most influential feature is the entropy of Flow Duration (refer to Table 1), while the third L-moment of the eighth feature, Flow IAT Min, has the least impact on the final prediction. Notably, the key contributors to the final prediction are features based on entropy, followed by L-moment features, mean, and standard deviation.

Mutual Information, on the other hand, measures how much information a feature provides about class labels. It excels in capturing both linear and nonlinear relationships between features and class labels, making it particularly valuable for feature selection in cases involving non-linear classification challenges. This method effectively identifies features that hold substantial information for accurate classification. Figure 4 showcases the most important features as determined by mutual information analysis. Similar to the ANOVA analysis, the entropy of the first features stands out as the most influential, while the fourth L-moment of the ninth feature, Fwd Packetss, is the least influential.

RFE is a feature selection technique that recursively removes irrelevant features from the dataset, and the remaining features are used to train the model. This process continues until a pre-defined number of features is reached, or the model's performance stops improving. RFE assigns a rank to each feature based on its contribution to the model's accuracy. Figure 5 shows, the ten feature that have the most contribution to the final prediction. As the figure shows the entropy of third feature, Total Length of Fwd Packets, and the L-kurtosis of the ninth feature, Fwd Packetss, have the most and least contribution to the decision, respectively. Furthermore, entropy, L4-moments, L-kurtosis, L-skewness, and the standard deviation are the main contributors to the final prediction.

SHAP, on the other hand, is a model-agnostic technique that explains the output of any machine learning model based on the contribution of each feature to the final prediction. SHAP values provide a measure of how much each feature contributes

Fig. 3: Feature ranking based on ANOVA.

to the output. Positive SHAP values indicate a feature contributes positively to the output, while negative SHAP values indicate a feature contributes negatively to the output. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the SHAP feature importance and SHAP summary plots for the ten most effective features, respectively.

The SHAP feature importance plot is a bar chart that shows the top N=10 features ranked by their importance. The importance is calculated based on the average absolute SHAP value over all the instances in the dataset. The feature importance

Fig. 4: Feature ranking based on Mutual Information.

Fig. 5: Feature ranking based on RFE and random forest.

plot provides a quick way to identify the most important features in the model and to compare the relative importance of different features. From Figure 6, it is evident that each feature makes a comparable contribution towards both classes. Additionally, upon comparison with the RFE feature ranking, the SHAP outcomes reflect a nearly identical feature set with equivalent rankings.

On the other hand, the SHAP summary plot is a scatter plot that shows the impact of each feature on the model output for all the instances in the dataset. The x-axis represents the SHAP value for each feature, and the y-axis represents the feature value. The summary plot provides a visual summary of the distribution of SHAP values for each feature and how they relate to the prediction. Figure 7 exhibits a summary plot of normal traffic. For instance, the third feature exhibits a negative impact on predicting normal traffic for higher values of entropy (highlighted in red), while lower values (indicated in blue) have a positive effect on the prediction of normal traffic. Similarly, the fourth L-moment of the tenth feature has a positive impact on classifying normal traffic for higher values, while lower values have a negative impact.

Fig. 6: SHAP feature importance plot.

All discussed results so far are based on binary classification of normal traffic and attack traffic, including all four types of attacks. In the final section, we expand the analysis to include five traffic classes, namely normal, goldeneye DoS, Hulk DoS, slowhttp Dos, and slowloris Dos attacks. This analysis assesses the statistical features' capacity for multi-class classification and separating various types of DoS attacks. We perform ANOVA analysis, Mutual Information, RFE analysis, and SHAP feature importance plot to determine the primary contributors for multi-class classification tasks. Figure 8 presents the ranking results for the ANOVA analysis. In the context of multi-class classification, similar to binary classification, the first feature's entropy outperforms other features. Mutual Information produces a ranking similar to ANOVA analysis, which is evident in Figure 9. Additionally, Figure 10 and 11 depict RFE and

Fig. 7: SHAP summary plot.

feature importance plots for multi-class applications, respectively. A comparison of these two figures reveals that, with minor discrepancies, both analyses yield a similar ranking of features for multi-class classification.

Despite slight variations in feature rankings between multi-class and binary-class scenarios, the feature sets are quite similar for Mutual Information, RFE, and SHAP analysis. However, ANOVA analysis shows a difference when compared to binary classification. In the case of binary classification, most features are selected from entropy, L-moments, and standard statistical moments. In contrast, for multi-class classification, the majority of selected features come from entropy and standard statistical moments. To summarize, the results indicate that entropy-based features play a primary role in classification for both binary and multi-class scenarios, followed by L-moments features.

5 Computational Complexity Analysis of Statistical Features

In the realm of data analysis, the selection of statistical features can significantly impact the efficiency of the analytical process, especially when dealing with large datasets. Understanding the computational complexity of these features is crucial for informed decision-making in selecting the most appropriate tools. In this section, we conduct a thorough analysis of the computational complexities associated with various statistical features, shedding light on their efficiency and performance characteristics.

Mean (Average): The mean, a measure of central tendency, boasts a linear complexity of $O(n)$, making it a quick and efficient calculation.

Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis: These fundamental statistical features exhibit linear complexities, with $O(n)$ computational requirements, enabling their widespread use for data analysis tasks.

Fig. 8: Feature ranking based on ANOVA for multi-class use case.

Fig. 9: Feature ranking based on Mutual Information for multi-class use case.

Entropy: As an information-theoretic measure, entropy has a quadratic complexity ($O(n^2)$). This quadratic nature arises from estimating probabilities and iterating through the data, which warrants careful consideration when applied to large datasets.

Hurst Parameter: The computational complexity of the Hurst parameter can vary depending on the chosen method, with options of $O(n \log n)$ and $O(n^2)$. The choice of method plays a critical role in optimizing the analysis process.

Fig. 10: Feature ranking based on RFE and random forest for multi-class use case.

Fig. 11: SHAP feature importance plot for multi-class use case

L-Moments : L-Moments demonstrate consistent efficiency with an $O(n \log n)$ complexity. This characteristic positions them as versatile tools for various applications in data analysis. This comprehensive computational complexity analysis offers valuable insights into the efficiency and performance characteristics of statistical features.

Table 4: Computational complexities cost of statistical features.

Statistical Feature	Complexity
Mean (Average)	$O(n)$
Variance	$O(n)$
Skewness	$O(n)$
Kurtosis	$O(n)$
Entropy	$O(n^2)$
Hurst Parameter	$O(n \log n)$ or $O(n^2)$
$\lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \tau_3, \tau_4$	$O(n \log n)$

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we investigate the potential of utilizing a diverse range of statistical features to detect LDoS attack. Our goal is to enhance the existing knowledge on LDoS attack detection by offering valuable insights into the applicability and effectiveness of statistical moments as a fundamental feature set. Through our research, we aim to contribute to the understanding of how statistical moments can be utilized in detecting LDoS attacks, thereby expanding the range of available techniques for addressing this security concern. By exploring the potential of statistical moments as a basic feature set, we strive to provide meaningful contributions to the field and facilitate future advancements in LDoS attack detection methodologies. Our approach involves analyzing a dataset column by column, extracting 176 statistical features, and utilizing them to distinguish between LDoS traffic and legitimate traffic using various machine learning algorithms. Additionally, we employ ANOVA, Mutual Information, RFE, and SHAP analysis to identify the top 10 features that significantly influence the final prediction for both binary and multi-class classification tasks. Our results reveal that entropy-based features are the primary contributors to classification in both cases, followed by L-moments features. These findings suggest that statistical features can be highly effective for LDoS attack detection. An important area for further investigation and exploration in our future work is the potential issue of flows that are partially malicious and partially benign with the same timestamp. This challenge necessitates further research to develop more sophisticated feature engineering approaches and incorporate advanced machine learning techniques. By addressing this issue, we aim to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of LDoS attack detection systems in practical scenarios. Furthermore, although SHAP provides details related to the contribution of features to the prediction, it does not provide information related to causal inference. Therefore, we will consider approaches to evaluate the contribution of features to detection, and we will also explore the inclusion of statistical features in the frequency domain.

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